

Chief scientist office, Scottish Executive

Data management plan required?	Encouraged
RDM policy Link	No
Definition of data	Not specified
Length of data management plan	Not specified
DMP template/ requirements	Not specified
Required data repository	UK Data Archive
Time for data release	There will be a limited period of exclusive use allowed.
Time for long-term storage of data	Raw data and/ or results must be stored for a minimum of 5 years after completion of the project.
Costings	Not specified
Last updated	Not known
Contact Details	alan.mcnair@gov.scot
Comments	Subsequent secondary use will acknowledge the original research.

Documents used:

CSO Standard terms and conditions

<https://www.cso.scot.nhs.uk/wp-content/uploads/CSO-Standard-Conditions-of-Grant-Response-Mode-v1-5.pdf>**Accessed:** May 2018 (V1.5)